

Low Temperature Electron Spin Resonance Study of MnPS₃

Antiferromagnetic Single Crystal

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ABSTRACT

Van der Waals MnPS₃ compound belonging to the class of Néel-type antiferromagnets (AFM) has recently emerged as promising two-dimensional material for spintronic applications. In this work, we report on the Electron Spin Resonance (ESR) study of a MnPS₃ single crystal across the Néel-transition temperature ($T_N = 78$ K) for the magnetic field applied in the directions parallel and perpendicular to the crystallographic c axis. Furthermore, the ESR angular dependence at a temperature near T_N has been investigated. We observe multiple resonance modes with antiferromagnetic, ferromagnetic and paramagnetic characters. In addition, we reveal the occurrence of complex spin-spin correlations and a magnetic-topological Berezinskii–Kosterlitz–Thouless (BKT) phase transition (*i.e.* bound vortex-antivortex pairs) at T_{BKT} with T_{BKT} / T_N typically found in two-dimensional magnets.

INTRODUCTION

Layered van der Waals magnets, also referred as 2D magnets, are gaining more and more interest because of their rich physical phenomena and potential applications in spintronics.^{1,2} Particularly

appealing is the possibility to form heterostructures from mechanical exfoliation of bulk crystals down to the few-layer or even monolayer. These heterostructures would be functional to realize magnetic tunnelling junctions for spin-transfer torque (STT), spin-orbit torque (SOT) and thermally assisted (TA) magnetic random-access memories (MRAM), which are considered as the only non-volatile memories with high-density, endurance and fast writing speed.^{3, 4}

The most widely studied 2D magnets are those with ferromagnetic (FM) ground state,⁵ whereas research on antiferromagnetic (AFM) 2D magnets has not proceeded at the same pace mainly because of the difficulties to detect detailed magnetic properties in materials with weak or null magnetization in the ground state. Nevertheless, several recent experiments have confirmed the possibility to store magnetic information with AFM materials.⁶⁻¹⁰ With respect to FM materials, AFM-based devices provide the advantage to avoid unintentional magnetic crosstalk between neighboring devices because of zero stray fields. Thus AFM 2D magnets would enable magnetic storage robust against magnetic field perturbations.⁸

Among the class of AFM 2D magnets, the MPS_3 ($M = Fe, Ni, Mn$) family stand out because magnetic order, spin dimensionality as well as transition temperature depend on M despite alike crystal structures. $FePS_3$ and $NiPS_3$ show zigzag-like AFM ordering, whereas $MnPS_3$ shows a Néel-type AFM configuration where the spin of each magnetic site is anti-aligned with the two nearest neighbors.¹¹⁻¹³ In the ordered state $FePS_3$ and $MnPS_3$ show an easy axis perpendicular to the crystallographic plane, whereas $NiPS_3$ possesses an easy plane coinciding with the atomic planes.¹⁴ Furthermore, the bulk Néel temperatures for $FePS_3$,¹⁵⁻¹⁷ $NiPS_3$,¹⁸ and $MnPS_3$,¹⁴ are 118 K, 155 K and 78 K, respectively.¹⁹

Despite the lower Néel temperature, $MnPS_3$ is particularly attractive because bulk-like magnetism might persist down to the monolayer limit,²⁰ as well as because of interesting phenomena like induced ferromagnetism²¹ and spin flop transition¹³ at low temperature in presence of magnetic

field. Recently, the possibility to observe a magnetic-topological Berezinskii–Kosterlitz–Thouless (BKT) phase transition which stabilizes a bound vortex-antivortex pair at BKT temperature, T_{BKT} , has been suggested.^{22, 23}

Nevertheless, a distinction must be made between type-A layered AFMs, which possess ferromagnetic coupling within the layers, and Néel layered AFMs where spins are arranged antiferromagnetically within each layer. In the former, magnetic tunnelling junctions can be realized by changing the relative orientation between the layers. In the latter, spin-filtering effects does not occur and the magnetic properties cannot be monitored with conventional transport measurements.²⁰

Therefore, the magnetic characterization of Néel layered AFMs requires alternative techniques.

Electron Spin Resonance (ESR) and the related electron Paramagnetic (EPR), Antiferromagnetic Resonance (AMR) and Ferromagnetic Resonance (FMR) techniques have been proved to be powerful tools to study 2D magnet.²⁴ Temperature magnetic resonance field, linewidth and intensity enable the characterization of the magnetic transition phases, whereas the angular dependence of the magnetic resonances in single crystal provides unambiguous determination of the magnetic axes.

Recently, ESR has shown to be a valid tool to assess the spin dimensionality and find signatures for magnetic topological phase transitions of 2D magnets in the bulk 3D form from combined angular and temperature dependences of the spectral linewidth supported by theoretical modelling.^{25, 26} This is possible because 2D magnets possess very weak interlayer magnetic coupling relative to the in-plane coupling, which makes them inherently 2D even in the bulk form.

Previous ESR studies on MnPS_3 have been reported by a few groups at conventional X-band frequency²³ as well as at frequencies ranging 8-330 GHz.^{22, 27} The high frequencies/strong magnetic studies have reported the occurrence of AFM and paramagnetic resonance branches^{22, 27} as well as the occurrence of a transition from 3D-like character of the spin wave excitation to a 2D-XY scaling regime boosted by the strong magnetic field.²² Whereas, at X-band only a single broad line has been reported in the temperature region above the Néel temperature ($T > 100$ K),^{23, 28, 29}

Here, we investigate the temperature and angular dependence of the ESR spectra on a MnPS₃ single crystal in the relevant temperature range crossing T_N from room temperature to liquid helium temperature. Our ESR spectra show the occurrence of resonance branches previously not reported already above the transition temperature $T_N = 78$ K, revealing a complex magnetic behavior of MnPS₃ with mixed ferromagnetic and antiferromagnetic phases which could be responsible for the formation of magnetic topological phases. Finally, we discuss and interpret the ESR based on the BKT model of the ESR linewidth.

METHODS

Crystal synthesis

MnPS₃ was made by direct reaction in ampoule from elements with subsequent chemical vapor transport crystal growth. Manganese (99.95 %, -100 mesh, Mateck, Germany), phosphorus (99.9999 %, 2-6 mm granules, Wuhan Xinrong New Materials Co., China) and sulphur (99.9999 %, 2-6 mm granules, Wuhan Xinrong New Materials Co., China) were placed in quartz ampoule (50 x 250 mm) in stoichiometric ratio corresponding to 30 g of MnPS₃. To facilitate chemical vapor transport, sulfur and phosphorus were used in 1 at % excess together with 0.5 g of iodine (99.9 %, Fisher Scientific, USA). The ampoule was sealed under high vacuum using oxygen-hydrogen welding torch and diffusion pump with liquid nitrogen trap (pressure $< 1 \times 10^{-3}$ Pa). The ampoule was placed in muffle furnace and heated on 450 °C for 50 hours and subsequently in steps on 500°C for 50 hours, on 600°C for 50 hours and on 700 °C for 50 hours. The heating rate between each step was 0.2°C/min. Subsequently the ampoule was placed in two-zone furnace for crystal growth. First the growth zone was heated on 750 °C and source zone on 500 °C. After 2 days the gradient was reversed and the source zone was heated on 750 °C while the growth zone temperature was decreased from 700 °C to 650 °C over a period of 5 days and for following 5 days was growth zone

kept on 650 °C. On the end of crystal growth procedure was growth zone heated on 350 °C, while the source zone was kept on 150 °C for 2 hours. The ampoule was opened in argon filled glovebox, where crystals with size over 1 cm were separated.

X-ray diffraction (XRD)

The crystal structure was characterized using X-ray diffractometer (XRD, Bruker D8 with Cu K α radiation, Germany), Raman (using a 532 nm laser, Renishaw, England), and transmission electron microscopy (TEM, EFTEM Jeol 2200 FS microscope, Japan).

X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS)

The surface composition of the samples was further studied with X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) using SPECS spectrometer equipped with a monochromatic Al K α X-ray source (1486.7 eV) and a hemispherical electron analyzer Phoibos 150. The survey spectra were recorded with E_p set to 100 eV, the high-resolution spectra of the core lines with E_p set to 20 eV. The base chamber pressure during the acquisitions was at 10⁻⁹ mbar or lower. Due to a heavy charge development on the samples' surface, a low-energy electron flow generated by an electron flood gun has been used to compensate the charge buildup.

Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM)

TEM including high resolution TEM and SAED were recorded on an EFTEM Jeol 2200 FS microscope, Japan. Energy dispersive X-ray (EDX) analysis was also conducted using a detector of Oxford Instruments in the same instrument.

Raman

The Raman resonance spectra were recorded using a confocal Raman microscope (Renishaw, UK) with a DPSS Nd-YAG laser (532 nm), 20x lens, 0.5 mW on sample (1 %), 20 s exposure time, 30 scans.

Electron Spin Resonance

Samples were mounted on a suprasil quartz rod and into a goniometer with $\frac{1}{2}$ degree sensitivity for ESR crystal rotation measurements. A flat crystal with surface size $2 \times 3 \text{ mm}^2$ and thickness $< 1 \text{ mm}$ was selected to avoid saturation and distortion of the ESR signal. The ESR spectra were recorded with a Varian E15 spectrometer coupled to a Bruker super high Q cavity operated at X-band ($\sim 9.4 \text{ GHz}$). The static magnetic field was modulated at 100 kHz with modulation amplitude of 4 Gauss . The magnetic field was monitored continuously with an electronic counter and a Hall probe. Sample temperatures in the range $4\text{--}300 \text{ K}$ were obtained with an Oxford ESR 900 cryostat. A DPPH sample was used as reference to determine the g -factors. MatLab generated routines were used to fit the spectra. Peak-to-peak linewidths ΔH were calculated from the full-width half maximum $\Delta H_{1/2}$ obtained from the Lorentzian fit with the relation: $\Delta H = \Delta H_{1/2} / \sqrt{3}$.

RESULTS

The X-ray diffraction (XRD) structure of MnPS_3 is shown in **Figure 1a**. The diffraction pattern presented in **Figure S1** in the Supplementary Information (SI) indicates the high crystalline quality and a well-ordered structure of the MnPS_3 single crystal with $C2/m$ space group. EDS mapping images shown in **Figure 1b** provide a spatial distribution of manganese (Mn), phosphorus (P), and sulfur (S) within the sample, confirming the homogeneous composition and elemental distribution across the crystal. The corresponding EDS spectrum of MnPS_3 in **Figure S2** shows the ratio of Mn:P:S in weight is $14.8\%: 8.4\%: 25.6\%$, corresponding to the atomic ratio of $1.0: 1.01: 2.96$, matching well with designed stoichiometric ratio of compound's formula. High-resolution TEM (HRTEM) reveals the atomic lattice with a measured lattice spacing (d) of 3.57 \AA for the (111) planes, consistent with known crystallographic data for MnPS_3 (**Figure 1c** and **1d**). The SAED pattern displays sharp and well-defined diffraction spots, confirming the crystal direction as [001] and indicating high crystallinity and structural integrity (**Figure 1e**). These results are also supported by additional XPS and Raman studies reported in **Figures S3** and **S4** in the Supplementary Materials.

Figure 1. (a) Crystal structure of MnPS₃. (b) EDS mapping indicating the elemental distribution of Mn, P, and S within MnPS₃. (c) TEM image and corresponding High-resolution TEM image with an inset showing the lattice fringe spacing. (d) SAED pattern along the [001] zone axis of MnPS₃.

Figure 2 shows the temperature dependence of the ESR spectra recorded for the external magnetic field parallel ($H \parallel c$) and perpendicular ($H \perp c$) to the crystallographic c axis. In both cases there is a single ESR peak centered at $H_r = 342 \text{ mT}$ and $H_r = 339 \text{ mT}$, respectively whose resonance fields are essentially independent on temperature. We refer to the central resonance peak as *PM* due to its paramagnetic behavior as it will be discussed below. Upon cooling for $H \parallel c$ we observe the emergence of a secondary resonance branch which overlaps with the PM signal at $T \sim 150 \text{ K}$, and it

evolves down to $T \sim 50$ K. Hereafter, we refer to this signal as *mode I*. For $T < 94$ K another resonance signal, *mode II*, appears from very low magnetic field values.

For $H \perp c$ only one resonance signal is observed down to $T \sim 50$ K with a weak contribution from *mode I* appearing for $T \sim 100$ K.

Figure 2 ESR spectra recorded as function of the temperature for $H \parallel c$ (a) and $H \perp c$ (b). The dashed lines are guide for the eyes to single out the different resonance lines: PM, *mode I* and *mode II*.

We extract the ESR intensity, resonance peak (H_r) and peak-to-peak linewidth (ΔH) as function of the temperature and rotation for $H \parallel c$ and $H \perp c$ from fitting of the spectra to Lorentzian functions.

In **Figure 3** are reported stack plots of the simulation and the experimental data for the canonical orientations and for two representative temperatures, namely $T = 65$ K and $T = 90$ K.

Figure 3 ESR spectra recorded for $H \perp c$ and $H \parallel c$ for $T \sim 65$ K (a) and $T \sim 90$ K (b). Black curves are experimental data and red curves are the simulations. Spectra are off-set along the vertical axes for clarity.

We now describe in detail the temperature dependence of *PM*, *mode I* and *mode II* reported in **Figure 4**. *PM* intensity for $H \parallel c$ increases by lowering the temperature down to $T \sim 130$ K before decreasing at lower temperatures. *Mode I* intensity decreases monotonously from room temperature to $T \sim 80$ K. For $T < 100$ K the *mode II* emerges with a rapidly increasing intensity reaching a maximum at $T \sim 74$ K before quickly decreasing at lower temperatures. *PM* intensity for $H \perp c$ increases by lowering the temperature down to $T \sim 120$ K before decreasing at lower temperatures and vanishing for $T < 50$ K.

The resonance field for *PM* is essentially independent on temperature for both orientations $H \parallel c$ and $H \perp c$, whereas its resonance linewidth ΔH increases monotonously upon cooling till $T \sim 150$ K, and at lower temperatures it rapidly broadens for $T < 100$ K. Resonance field for *mode I* for both $H \perp c$ and $H \parallel c$ separates from *PM* for $T < 150$ K and shifts to lower fields reaching a minimum for $T \sim 100$ K before shifting to higher resonance fields. The resonance field of *mode II* for $H \parallel c$ appears from zero field at $T \sim 100$ K and shifts linearly to higher magnetic fields.

Figure 4 Temperature dependence of the ESR intensity (a), peak-to-peak linewidth (b), for the PM and mode II resonances for $H \perp c$ and $H \parallel c$. In (b), dashed lines are fittings of the data to the BKT model. Resonance fields for $H \perp c$ (c) and $H \parallel c$ (d). Line are guides for the eyes.

The angular dependence of the resonance field, H_r , and peak-to-peak linewidth, ΔH , obtained from the best fit at $T = 75$ K for PM and mode II are reported in **Figure 5**. H_r and ΔH for the PM signal depend weakly on the orientation of the crystal with respect to the magnetic field, whereas a pronounced angular dependence is observed for mode II. H_r and ΔH show a minimum for $H \parallel c$ and a maximum for $H \perp c$.

Figure 5 Angular dependence of the resonance field (a) and ESR linewidth (b) for the *PM* and *mode II* ESR signals for $T = 75K$.

DISCUSSION

The observed *PM* signal is associated to a paramagnetic phase in the $MnPS_3$ crystal because it is isotropic and its resonance field is essentially temperature independent. This interpretation is also supported by the analysis of its ESR intensity which increases for lower temperatures in agreement with the Curie's law for paramagnets. The decrease of the ESR intensity for $T < 150 K$ indicates the onset of an antiferromagnetic phase where the antiparallel alignment of the Mn spins effectively decreases the magnetic susceptibility. The shift of *mode I* to lower and higher fields in the temperature region 150-90 K (**Figure 4c** and **4d**) suggests the occurrence of mixed antiferromagnetic and ferromagnetic phases. The last one is supported by *mode II* which appears from zero magnetic field at $T \sim 90K$ which corresponds to the temperature upturn of *mode I*. For $T < 90K$ *mode II* shifts quickly to high fields at lower temperatures thus suggesting its AFM nature further corroborated by the quenching of its ESR intensity. These results elucidate the complex mixing of AFM and FM where the degree of mixing might give arise to different spin arrangements.

The van der Waals nature of $MnPS_3$ crystals suggests that magnetic order could be confined in a 2-dimensional space and described by the XY spin model below the magnetic phase transition. Within

a such model topological effects can lead to the formation of local spin arrangements like bound vortex and antivortex pairs as predicted by the BKT theory. The ESR spectra can capture the signature of the BKT transition both in the temperature and angular dependence of the ESR linewidth. The ESR linewidth follows the temperature dependence according to the BKT model³⁰:

$$\Delta H(T) = \Delta H_{\infty} \exp\left(\frac{3b}{\sqrt{\frac{T}{T_{BKT}}}-1}\right) + \Delta H_0 \quad (1)$$

where in the first term, ΔH_{∞} is the linewidth to infinity, $b = \pi/2$, ΔH_0 takes into account an offset of the room temperature linewidth (**Table 1**).

BKT model	ΔH_{∞} (mT)	b	ΔH_0 (mT)	T_{BKT} (K)
$H \parallel c$	4 ± 1	$\pi/2$	183 ± 10	28 ± 1
$H \perp c$	17 ± 5	$\pi/2$	170 ± 20	25 ± 3

Table 1 Results of the fitting to **Equation 1**

From the fitting of the data in **Figure 3** (b) we find a substantial agreement between the T_{BKT} obtained for both orientations within the fitting error bars. The value of T_{BKT} is always below the magnetic ordering temperature T_N , with a ratio $\frac{T_{BKT}}{T_N} \sim 0.47 - 0.48$ as typically found in quasi-two-dimensional magnets.²⁶

The angular dependence of the resonance field and linewidth of the *PM* resonance below $T \sim 90$ K is very weak confirming its isotropic character in the entire temperature range investigated. A pronounced ESR angular dependence is observed for *mode II*. In order to search for the formation of bound vortex and antivortex pairs we fit the ESR resonance linewidth angular dependence of *mode II* at $T = 75$ K. There is an experimental evidence that the ESR linewidth in the regime of mixed FM and AFM phases responsible for the formation of topological phases deviate from a simple $\cos^2\varphi$ dependence:

$$\Delta H(\varphi) = A(3\cos^2\varphi - 1) + \Delta H_{0\parallel} ; \quad (2a)$$

Instead, it assumes what it is usually referred to a W -like shape which can be fitted with the following equation:

$$\Delta H(\varphi) = B(3\cos^2\varphi - 1)^2 + \Delta H_{0\perp} ; \quad (2b)$$

The fitting of the ESR linewidth to **Equation 2a** suggests the occurrence of only one dominant magnetic phase (*i.e.*, FM), whereas the ESR linewidth at $T = 75$ K clearly deviates from a $\cos^2\varphi$ -like shape leaning more towards a W -like shape. This argument is supported by the fitting of the data to **Equation 2b** with fitting parameters: $B = 153 \pm 7$ mT and $\Delta H_{0\perp} = 22 \pm 6$ mT.

CONCLUSION

We have reported on an temperature and angular study on a MnPS₃ single crystal by ESR at conventional X-band frequency. We have observed the occurrence of a paramagnetic phase along with multiple resonance modes above and below the Néel temperature both for the magnetic field applied along and perpendicular to the crystallographic c axis. We have ascribed these modes to competing AFM and FM interactions as suggested by their opposite shift of the resonance field. From the analysis of the resonance linewidth we have obtained evidence for spin-spin correlations at $T < T_N$ which we ascribe to the magnetic topological phase transition and to the formation of bound vortex and antivortex pairs of the BKT model.

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Data Availability Statement

The datasets generated during and/or analyzed during the study are accessible via the Zenodo repository: <https://zenodo.org/records/13692266>

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